

Flow State of Composite Materials in the Forging Die during the Molding Process

T. Hirai¹⁾, T. Katayama²⁾, H. Hamada³⁾

1) Department of Mechanical Engineering, Doshisha University, Karasuma-higashiiru, Imadegawa-dori, Kamigyō-ku, Kyoto 602, Japan

2) Osaka Prefectural Industrial Research Institute, 4 Kaminabe-cho, Sakai 590, Japan

3) Osaka Municipal Technical Research Institute, 1-6-50, Morinomiya, Jotou-ku, Osaka 536, Japan

ABSTRACT

The compression molding process using SMC or BMC has been developed as a mass production technology. The long cycle time is an obstacle progress of this process, so that the reducing of the cycle time (Cycle-Up) has been required.

In this paper, the Up-Set Molding Process using the backward extrusion was proposed in the case of T-shaped canal and during this process the flow state and temperature distribution were analyzed by applying the FEM.

It is shown in the process that the temperature distribution is more uniform and higher than the ordinary forward extrusion process and the flow state of materials contributed to prevent the troubles. Therefore it is suggested that the procedure shown in this paper could reduce the cycle time and control the molding temperature which prevented the deformation of the products after releasing from the die.

INTRODUCTION

A molding method using matched dies has attracted wide attention on the mass production system for the fabrication of FRP. This molding method, however, has not been widely used due to the following problems.

The first problem lies in controlling the orientation of reinforcement in products. The fiber orientation, which influences the mechanical properties of products, is unpredictable because of the material flow in the compression molding process. The solution to this problem is to assure the estimation of the material flow under various molding conditions. It has been clarified that the material flow in matched dies in the molding process is affected by the dimensions of the die, closing die speed, charge pattern, and molding temperature. The molding temperature is the major factor for the material flow.

The second problem lies in reducing the cycle-time (Cycle-Up). The curing which is necessary after the compression molding process requires much time. A long cycle-time caused by the curing is the main obstruction to wide use of the molding method. The cycle-time can be shortened by employing a high molding temperature, but in this case the surface of products will lose its smoothness. The

surface defect results from a chemical reaction affected by high temperature. Therefore, the process has to be completed before the start of the chemical reaction. And uneven temperature distribution is liable to cause warp on products. Temperature distribution in the material should be suitable to obtain product without warp and surface defect in a shorter time. Optimum molding temperature should be determined in consideration of the above points.

In the previous paper the numerical analysis for the flow state and temperature distribution of the composite materials was made with the aid of an anisotropic pseudo-plastic flow model, and its governing equations included the heat conduction equation. The numerical calculation method which was used to obtain the temperature distribution and flow pattern is called "Progressive Step by Step Method" (1, 2).

In this paper, the conception of the conventional method using the forward extrusion is modified and Up-Set Molding Process (Up-Set Method) using the backward extrusion is proposed in order to shorten the cycle-time. The T-shaped region is adopted for the analysis because it appears universally in the case of products with rib. At first the heterogeneity of the material is shown by the experiment. Next the numerical analysis is carried out and it is pointed out that the flow state, in the case of the Up-Set Molding Process, is not affected by the heterogeneity of the material. Then the temperature distribution and flow pattern obtained by "Progressive Step by Step Method" are demonstrated, and the availability of the Up-Set Molding Process is discussed. Finally the numerical analysis is done using the practical dimensions of the die and molding conditions.

ASSUMPTIONS AND NUMERICAL CALCULATION METHOD

In this section the assumptions and numerical analysis are mentioned.

- 1) Although the resin shows a homogeneous and isotropic nature, it comes to show a heterogeneous nature when reinforcement is included. therefore, it might be assumed that the reinforcement is oriented along the tangential direction of stream line under the molding process as a tendency.
- 2) The composite materials show the anisotropic nature because of the fiber orientation of the reinforcement of the flow direction.
- 3) The viscosity of the material decreases according to the fall of temperature and a numerical analysis is done for such temperature range. As the flow characteristics of composites might be assumed that of pseudo-plastics, the analysis should be applied by the consideration on Lagrangian system. Simplifying it on the calculation in this paper, the deviated Eulerian system is adopted as following accordance with the progressing procedure.
- 4) The Progressive Step by Step Method can be used for the analysis at any stage of the molding process. According to the progress of the molding process (e.g. increment of the rib part), finite elements are added on the flow direction.

At first temperature distribution is calculated for the initial state and viscosity distribution is given based on the obtained temperature distribution. Next velocity distribution is calculated using the obtained viscosity distribution. In the Progressive Step by Step Method these procedures are repeated.

UP-SET MOLDING PROCESS

Schematic figures of the conventional method and the Up-Set Molding Process are shown in Fig.1. The (a) is the conventional method (forward extrusion type) in which the surface AB is downward. The (b) is the Up-Set Molding Process (backward extrusion type) in which the surface AB is fixed. The T-shape is adopted to show the figure of the product.

In the experiment, BMC is prepressed to a plate 6mm in thickness to orient it initially in the horizontal direction, and then three prepressed plates are piled up and the specimen is made by the piled plates. In the specimen, colored marks made of the same material as the specimen are buried in each lamina at definite intervals to obtain finite displacement vectors by measuring the locations of marks

Fig.1 Die Set for Experiment.

before and after the molding process. In the experiment, a Plasticine specimen is also used to compare with the BMC specimen.

Fig.2 shows the finite displacement vectors obtained by the experiment. The (a) and (b) are of BMC and the (c) and (d) are of Plasticine. The (a) and (c) are obtained by the conventional method, and the (b) and (d) are obtained by the Up-Set Molding Process. In the case of Plasticine symmetrical flows are obtained by both methods, while in the case of BMC asymmetrical flows are obtained. The difference of these flow patterns is caused by the heterogeneity of BMC, and the difference is smaller in the case of the Up-Set Molding Process.

To examine these phenomena the flow pattern in the case of extreme heterogeneity is calculated by numerical analysis. Fig.3 shows the finite element model. The part (a) is resin, in part (c) the reinforcement is oriented to the horizontal direction and in part (b) the reinforcement is oriented to the vertical direction.

Fig.3 Finite Element Model in the case of taking consideration into extreme Heterogeneity.

In Fig.4 the calculated results are shown. In the case of the conventional method an extreme upward vector is obtained as shown by the mark o, while in the Up-Set Molding Process symmetrical flow is obtained. In the conventional method, the abnormal flow (the upward vector) is caused by the heterogeneity given as the initial condition, while in the Up-Set Molding Process the effect of this heterogeneity is canceled. Thus an essentially heterogeneous material can be molded by using the Up-Set Molding Process.

In conclusion, it must be noticed that even if the canal is symmetrical the calculation of the flow state of the heterogeneous material based on only a half part of the canal may lead to a wrong result in the case of the conventional method, so that the calculation must be done with reference to all parts of the canal. On the other hand, in the case of the Up-Set Molding Process the calculation using a half part will be sufficient for the heterogeneous material.

Fig.4 Velocity Vectors obtained by Numerical Analysis.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Fig.5 shows the finite element model. Boundary conditions are given as follows;

Conventional Method		Up-Set Method	
A-B	$V_y=0.3\text{mm/sec}$	A-B	$V_y=0.0$
A-C,B-F	$V_x=0.0$	A-C,B-F	$V_x=0.0$
C-D,F-E	$V_x=V_y=0.0$	C-D,F-E	$V_y=0.3\text{mm/sec}$
Point D,E	$V_y=0.0$	D-E	$P=0.0\text{Pa}$
D-E	$P=0.0\text{Pa}$		

Concerning molding temperature, the lower die is kept at 80°C for increasing fluidity and in the upper die a higher temperature (140°C) than in the lower die is employed to harden the material. Compression is started after a 30-second interval.

(a) Conventional Method (b) Up-Set Molding Process
Fig.5 Finite Element Model.

Fig.6 and 7 show the velocity distribution and temperature distribution in the case of the conventional method and the Up-Set Method respectively. As compared with the initial step flow pattern in Fig.6-(a) and Fig.7-(a), at the rib entrance the flow is found to have a tendency to head for the rib wall in the conventional method. This tendency is strengthened in the Up-Set Method. At the final step Fig.6-(b) shows that the upper surface lamina is moving greatly toward the symmetrical axis and that the meander flow is obtained at the rib part. On the other

hand, in the Up-Set Method Fig.7-(b) shows uniform flow pattern in flange and rib parts.

Fig.6 Velocity Vectors obtained by Numerical Analysis in the case of Conventional Method.

Fig.7 Velocity Vectors obtained by Numerical Analysis in the case of Up-Set Molding Process.

Fig.8 Temperature Distribution obtained by Numerical Analysis in the case of Conventional Method.

Fig.9 Temperature Distribution obtained by Numerical Analysis in the case of Up-Set Molding Process.

Next temperature distribution which is a decisive factor for the Cycle-Up shows a higher level in the Up-Set Method. Especially comparing Fig.8-(c) and Fig. 9-(c) in the conventional method at rib part, low level temperature distribution is obtained, while in the Up-Set Method higher temperature is distributed along the symmetrical axis. Temperature distribution obtained 21.6 seconds after compression molding is shown in Fig.10. Comparing both cases higher level temperature and uniform distribution are obtained by the Up-Set Method. Relations of the compres-

sion step with curing time and temperature are shown in Fig.11. In the Up-Set Method the point of flange part reaches high temperature in the course of the compression process, and temperature in the internal point rises by heat conductivity. The tendency toward uniform temperature distribution is clear. According to the actual measurement of temperature distribution after the compression process in the case of T-shape, calorification by chemical reaction appears at the point of the rib in a shorter curing time. This fact shows that the mass of the material affects the generation of heat. Therefore, temperature distribution along the symmetrical axis as shown in Fig.9-(c) might hasten uniform cure in all of the part. In addition, the Up-Set Method can shorten the curing time because of the higher temperature level. From the results above, it is clear that the Up-Set Method is an effective molding process.

Fig.10 Temperature Distribution obtained by Numerical Analysis after completing Compression 21.6 seconds.

Fig.11 Temperature in the products rising curve.

Fig.12 Finite Element Model for Practical Product.

APPLICATION OF PRACTICAL MODEL

In this section, actual dimensions of the die and T-shaped canal are analyzed. In Fig.12 mesh division is shown. The initial thickness of flange part is 6.6mm and the width of rib is 5.0mm. Closing speed is 100mm/min. Molding temperature is the same as mentioned above.

The velocity distribution is shown in Fig.13-(a) shows the velocities of the second step, and the magnifying figures of the second and final step are shown in Fig.13-(b) and (c) respectively.

These figures indicate that the tendency to curve is decreased, in the rib part the flow meanders. Fig.14 shows the temperature distribution in each step. In the initial state (Fig.14-(a)), due to the small size of the specimen, the middle

part rises. However, in the compression molding, the form of temperature distribution is nearly the same because the closing speed is high (b)(c). Especially along the symmetrical axis 70°C remains. After 7.2 seconds (Fig.15-(a)) the part along the symmetrical axis which is about 70°C in Fig.14-(c) abruptly rises to 120°C . At the rib part after 36.0 seconds (Fig.15-(b)) the temperature distribution is uniform at 130°C - 140°C . In the surface lamina along the lower die, the rise of temperature is not seen during or after compression process. Especially the rear part of rib remains at a lower level of temperature (90°C).

Fig.13 Velocity Vectors obtained by Numerical Analysis in the case of Practical Product.

The optimum temperature distribution, which solves these problems, is as follows. First, as the temperature rises, the viscosity decreases and the material softens; at a certain temperature they begin to harden by polymerization. And a higher molding temperature will shorten the time at the minimum value of viscosity. Therefore, in spite of employing higher molding temperature, the compression process can be finished within the time which shows the minimum value viscosity because of the higher closing speed. To effectively cope with the lower level temperature at the rear part of rib, the molding temperature is rised at the rear part of rib in the lower die to produce uniform temperature distribution.

Fig.14 Temperature Distribution obtained by Numerical Analysis.

Fig.15 Temperature Distribution obtained by Numerical Analysis after Completing Compression.

CONCLUSION

The present authors propose an Up-Set Molding Process in which the conventional positions of "Upper" and "Lower" dies are reversed in order to shorten the cycle-time. Temperature distribution and flow pattern are analyzed by the "Progressive Step by Step Method". From the results and discussion, it is concluded that:

- 1) By using the Up-Set Molding Process, the flow pattern is not affected by heterogeneity of the materials and is found to show stability.
- 2) In the case of T-shaped canal, the Up-Set Molding Process is effective with regard to both flow pattern and temperature distribution.
- 3) An optimum temperature distribution is suggested in a practical case.

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